

TABLE 1—ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COPPER AND PHOSPHATE

Mix No.	Calcium in mg.		Wt% error	Copper in mg.		Wt% error	Phosphorus in mg.		Wt% error
	Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.	
I	4.018	4.020	0.049	5.893	5.893	0.00	9.500	9.500	0.00
II	19.640	19.635	0.025	32.087	32.125	0.118	47.500	47.500	0.00
III	10.020	10.025	0.049	15.888	15.899	0.088	23.750	23.780	0.12

TABLE 2—ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, CADMIUM AND PHOSPHATE

Mix No.	Calcium in mg.		Wt% error	Cadmium in mg.		Wt% error	Phosphate in mg.		Wt% error
	Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.	
I	40.24	40.22	0.049	11.24	11.232	0.0712	95.94	95.90	0.0417
II	100.20	100.25	0.049	33.72	33.7015	0.0549	47.500	47.500	0.00
III	19.640	19.640	0.00	112.40	112.395	0.0045	9.554	9.554	0.00

TABLE 3—ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COBALT AND PHOSPHATE

Mix No.	Calcium in mg.		Wt% error	Cobalt in mg.		Wt% error	Phosphate in mg.		Wt% error
	Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.	
I	4.018	4.020	0.049	5.893	5.893	0.00	9.500	9.500	0.00
II	100.20	100.22	0.019	17.679	17.678	0.005	47.500	47.500	0.00
III	19.640	19.648	0.041	88.495	88.495	0.001	23.750	23.761	0.046

NaOH was added till neutral followed by 5 ml of buffer pH~10. It was diluted to 100 ml and titrated against 0.01 M E.D.T.A. using Murexide indicator till a sharp colour change from greenish yellow to deep violet is obtained.

In another set (same for the three systems) from a same amount of the aliquot solution phosphate was precipitated as phosphomolybdate¹, filtered, dissolved in minimum volume of 0.1 M hot NaOH. The phosphate was reprecipitated as magnesium ammonium phosphate, separated by filtration, washed with 20% NH₄OH, dissolved in 0.6 M warm HCl and subsequently determined complexometrically².

In all the cases the filtrate after removal of phosphate as phosphomolybdate was made up to a convenient volume and estimated for the combined cations complexometrically. For the total Ca²⁺ and Cd²⁺, the procedure adopted was similar for Cd²⁺ as mentioned above except with an additional use of Mg-EDTA complexonate before titration. For the total Ca²⁺-Cu²⁺ and Ca²⁺-Co²⁺ ions the free acid was neutralised with 0.2 M NaOH and the complexometric procedure adopted was similar with copper and cobalt determinations respectively. The difference of E.D.T.A. consumed for the total cations and the individual titre values resulted in the amount of Ca⁺⁺ present in a given mixture.

The results of chemical analyses of different representative synthetic combination are given in Tables 1-3.

The method is rapid and accurate and can be used for those metal ions which form a solid pyridine-thiocyanate or pyridine-salicylic acid complex.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (PPM) acknowledges the financial grant by U. G. C.

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Determination of Dissociation Constants of Some Amino Acids. Part I. Use of Wet Volume Ratio Method

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Manuscript received 11 May 1979, revised 26 November 1979, accepted 4 March 1980

APPPLICATION of the ion exchangers of low cross linking as analytical tools is found in the determination of water content of organic solvents and solutions, studies in valencies of various ions

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NOTES

in electrolytic solutions, since according to the rise in the valencies the wet volume ratio will shrink proportionately. With the development of new types of ion exchangers¹, containing different active groups such as $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}_3$, $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$, $-\text{PO}(\text{OH})_2$, the possibilities of applying these in analytical procedures have greatly increased. Calvin Calmon² has used beads of Permutit QX for determining K_a values of some weak acids. The present authors have adopted the same technique for finding out dissociation constants of some amino acids.

In the present investigation, a 1% DVB cross linking were used (Permutit QX), since it was thought that with 0.5% DVB cross linking a soluble poly-electrolyte may be obtained. Another reason for selecting a higher cross linking of DVB was the greater power of selectivity of such polystyrene beads. Samuelson *et al*³ have confirmed that the selectivity of the resin phase increases with the degree of cross linking.

Experimental

The amino acids were obtained from British Drug House and were used as such. Permutit QX beads sieved through 30-50 mesh were chosen. The diameters of the beads varied between 0.22 to 0.91 mm. All the measurements of the diameters were made on an Earnest Leitz Wetzlar microscope with a camera Lucida arrangement for drawing. Broken spheres were separated by keeping the Permutit QX beads on a polished inclined plate and tapping the plate gently to roll of the spheres. The split spheres were observed to have stayed behind.

The degree of swelling of the single bead was determined by measuring the diameters in dry and wet state under the microscope. Table 1 below gives the results of swelling with 1 percent cross linking.

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE OF SWELLING OF BEADS USED, IN H_2O AND C_6H_6

Liquid	Single bead method (% degree of swelling)					
Distilled H_2O	22.79	22.24	22.88	22.86	22.69	22.78
Distilled C_6H_6	3.64	3.70	3.78	3.66	3.88	3.42

The selected beads were first observed under a microscope for their perfect spherical nature. They were washed thoroughly with distilled water and then kept for 24 hours under deionised water. The beads were then labelled and after lightly blotting off the adhered water, their diameters were measured under the microscope. For the purpose of calibration, the labelled beads were then soaked in various concentrations of AnalaR HCl and their dimensions measured before and after soaking. All

precautions were taken as recommended in literature^{4,5} in measuring microscopically the diameters of the single spheres in dry and wet state. The data are represented graphically in Fig. 1.

The wet volume to dry volume ratios for the amino acids studied in this investigation were determined by measuring microscopically the diameters of single spheres in the dry and wet state as done in the case of hydrochloric acid. A wide variation in sizes have been found from sphere to sphere owing, no doubt, to non-uniform polymerisation. Other relevant properties of 1% DVB-cross linking beads are set out in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THE PROPERTIES OF 1% DVB CROSS LINKED PERMUTIT QX EXCHANGER USED

Total exchange capacity	5.19 m. eq. per g.
Density (Dry)	1.17 g/ml (Pyknometer method)
Density (Wet)	47 g/lit (backwash and drain)
Mesh size	30
Degree of swelling	25

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 is a plot of normality of HCl vs wet volume ratio as drawn from the values obtained. The plot gives the average ratio for three spheres of the given cross linking of a particular concentration of HCl. In the determination of dissociation constants of the quoted amino acids, a single bead was kept in 1 ml 1N amino acid with 5 ml of 0.1N NaOH added, and then the diameter of the swollen bead was measured under the high power microscope. The bead was washed several times with 1N solution of amino acid (with added NaOH) in question, after it attained a maximum diameter as seen under the microscope, the specific solution was blotted out with filter paper and then washed with distilled H_2O . The diameter was rechecked and the process repeated at least six times with the bead to check the reliabilities of the swollen volume. Again,

this was not confined to a single sphere for a specific substance but as often as 4 to 5 spheres were used for determining the size for a particular amino acid. For a particular concentration of amino acid the bead was allowed to come to equilibrium with the solution under investigation by repeated additions of fresh solutions and the removal of the old solution by adsorbing it on fresh filter paper pieces. It was noted that for dilute solution, longer periods of contacts were necessary.

The initial results of Calmon² showed that the most deswelling takes place in HCl and the least in acetic acid whose $K_a = 1.75 \times 10^{-5}$ if concentrations of both are identical. Hence it is safe to assume that (1) the volume changes are entirely due to ions, (2) for a given wet volume ratios, concentration of the ions is the same as concentration of very strongly ionised electrolyte at the same volume ratio and, (3) if the volume ratio of an acid under investigation is compared with the volume ratio of HCl of same normality, then the corresponding H^+ ion concentration in the wet volume vs H^+ concentration curve for HCl should give H^+ ions liberated by the unknown acid.

Applying this criterion, H^+ ion concentration of Glycine, L-Proline, DL-Tryptophane, L-Valine, Serine and DL-Methionine were determined (last column, Table 3) and their pK_a values were found (Table 3).

TABLE 3—WET VOLUME RATIOS FOR AMINO ACIDS

Amino acid (1 N)	r_1 (nm) Wet	r_2 (nm) Dry	Wet-Vol ratio (mean)	H^+ ion con. (from fig. 1)
@ Glycine	0.5315 0.2525 0.6200	0.5925 0.2819 0.6902	0.720	0.074
@ L-Proline	0.3036 0.3221 0.4075	0.3476 0.3679 0.4652	0.665	0.101
* DL-Tryptophane	0.4218 0.5025 0.4150	0.4777 0.5702 0.4702	0.690	0.087
* L-Valine	0.5426 0.2601 0.4524	0.6109 0.2931 0.5101	0.700	0.0830
@ Serine	0.5928 0.4026 0.2220	0.6642 0.4517 0.2488	0.710	0.0815
@ DL-Methionine	0.6214 0.2614 0.8100	0.6980 0.2932 0.9101	0.705	0.0820

@ Solable in cold wa'er.

* Very soluble in hot water and hence solutions were made accordingly.

It will be observed that average of some three readings in each case has been reported. It is noticed that the H^+ ion concentration of the amino acid bears a linear relation (Fig. 2) with the wet volume ratio of the respective acids and hence it

FIG 2 WET VOLUME RATIO OF AMINO ACIDS

should be possible to calculate H^+ concentration of any amino acid in the series without any reference to the HCl wet volume plot.

The dissociation constants were calculated by the standard equation in which concentrations were used in place of activities. The pK_a values of amino acids were also determined by potentiometric titrations. The pK_a values in addition were obtained by potentiometric methods and are presented in Table 4 along with those obtained by wet volume ratio method. Incidentally, the pK_a values obtained by the authors by potentiometry in situ agree well with those reported in literature.

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF pK_a VALUES BY BEAD METHOD AND POTENTIOMETRIC METHOD

Amino acid	pK_a (bead method)	pK_a (Potentiometric method)
Glycine	9.86	9.98
L-Proline	10.68	10.32
DL-Tryptophane	9.55	9.42
L-Valine	9.72	9.75
Serine	9.24	9.02
DL-Methionine	9.34	9.46

It need not be mentioned here that only second dissociation constants will be obtained in the present case as the amino acids have been rendered into their sodium salts.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (Leela Pardeshi) is grateful to Dr. K. A. Thakar, Professor and Head, Chemistry Department, Marathwada University for allowing her to carry out post-doctoral work in the Laboratory.

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Sorption and Desorption Studies of Crystal Violet and Malachite Green on and from Synthetic Zeolites 3A and AW500

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*Manuscript received 27 November 1979,
accepted 20 December 1979*

CRYSTAL violet and malachite green, which are triphenylmethane dyes, were used for interaction with synthetic zeolites 3A and AW500. The interacted samples have been studied by thermogravimetric, photometric and infrared spectroscopic methods. The zeolite 3A was in powder form while the other was in 1/16" cylindrical pellet form. Their characteristics are known from earlier studies¹⁻³.

Experimental

The zeolites were kept in contact with aqueous solutions of the two dyes for several days. They were heated from time to time to effect maximum interaction and later kept inside the refrigerator also for several days. The zeolites were filtered off from the excess liquid and dried in air. The thermogravimetric studies were carried out on a thermobalance supplied by the Fertilizer Corporation of India, Sindri, at a heating rate of 10°/minute between 293 and 1073°K. Absorption data were collected between 200 and 1000 nm by means of a spectrophotometer with reflectance attachment (Model

VSK-2P). The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer instrument (Model 577) between 4000 and 200 cm⁻¹ in cesium iodide. The elemental analyses were done on a Thomas CH-Analyzer 35 and Coleman N-Analyzer 29. The relevant data have been reproduced in Table 1.

Discussion

The zeolite samples start losing weight around 353°K and process of weight loss continues till 873°K for malachite green-sorbed AW500 and 933°K for the other three samples. Maximum weight loss for dehydration occurs around 430°K and for the desorption of the dyes at about 530°K. Thermogravimetric data were utilised for evaluating the kinetic parameters of the weight loss sequence, on the basis of the relation, $g(\alpha) = [-\log_e(1-\alpha)]^{1/n} = Kt = ze^{-E/RT}$, suggested by Avrami⁴ and Erofejev⁵ where K is the specific reaction rate constant and E is the corresponding activation energy of the isothermal process. Values of α were calculated from

$$\alpha = \frac{(W_t - W_i)}{(W_o - W_i)}$$

where W_t is the indicated weight at time or temperature, t ; W_o is the initial sample weight; and W_i is the residual weight at the end of the process under study. The plots between $g(\alpha)$ and time are non-linear for $n=1, 2$ and 3 . These plots show that the thermal events occur at two different rates. The plots for $\log_e [g(\alpha)/T^2]$ vs $1000/T$ are straight lines having different slopes for dehydration and desorption of sorbed species for $n=1, 2$ and 3 . Both the processes are first order reactions⁶. The extent of dye-sorption is obtained from the photometric data as well as the percentages of carbon in the various samples. It is clear that crystal violet is more extensively sorbed than malachite green and zeolite 3A exhibits greater capacity for dye-sorption compared to AW500. IR spectra of the samples indicate that the sorption occurs by hydrogen bonding atleast in the case of 3A as the absorption bands due to water at about 3500 and 1650 cm⁻¹ are broadened considerably due to the presence of the sorbed species. This broadening effect is not pronounced in the case of zeolite AW500.

TABLE 1

Zeolite	Weight Loss %	Carbon %	Hydrogen %	Nitrogen %
Crystal violet sorbed 3A	28.5	4.88	2.76	Negligible
Crystal violet sorbed AW500	18.7	1.70	2.24	"
Malachite green sorbed 3A	23.9	1.34	1.84	"
Malachite green sorbed AW500	18.6	Negligible	1.57	"